

Synthesis and Characterisation of Copper(II) Complexes of 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Thioureas

T. SUDERSHAN, CH. TIRUPATAIAH, D. RADHARAMANA and S. SRIHARI*

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 28 April 1993, revised 8 November 1993, accepted 9 December 1993

The complexes of Cu^{II} with ligands derived from some 2-amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and benzoyl isothiocyanates have been synthesised and characterised by analytical, magnetic, conductance, thermal and ir, electronic and esr spectral data. The ligands (L's) exhibit neutral, bidentate behaviour bonding to Cu^{II} through benzoyl oxygen and keto sulphur. The complexes, with the composition $[\text{CuL}(\text{OAc})_2]$, conform to square-planar geometry. From the esr spectra of the complexes, the bonding parameters characterising the covalency have been calculated and discussed.

The biological activity of sulphur containing compounds is well documented. Various thiourea derivatives, in this respect, have been successfully screened for various biological activities¹. 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles, as important a class of compounds as thioureas, are also physiologically active². 1,3,4-Oxadiazole thioureas, composed of biologically potent 1,3,4-oxadiazole and thiourea moieties, have been reported to be endowed, amongst others, with pesticidal properties³. These systems possess various bonding sites and can act as chelating ligands. The biological activity associated with these systems has been traced, in most of the cases, to their ability to chelate metals present in biosystem. The promising nature, in terms of biological activity, of these systems has prompted us to investigate their ligating behaviour towards transition metal ions. As a part of this, we now report the synthesis of the complexes of Cu^{II} , a biologically as well as chemically important metal, with ligands : *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-(5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [BPOT], *N*-*p*-methylbenzoyl-*N'*-(5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [MBPOT], *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-(5-*p*-tolyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [BTOT], *N*-*p*-methylbenzoyl-*N'*-(5-*p*-tolyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [MBTOT], *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-(5-*p*-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [BCOT], *N*-*p*-methylbenzoyl-*N'*-(5-*p*-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [MBCOT], *N*-*o*-chlorobenzoyl-*N'*-(5-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea

[CBMOT], *N*-*p*-anisoyl-*N'*-(5-*p*-chlorophenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [ACOT], *N*-*p*-anisoyl-*N'*-(5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [APOT], *N*-*p*-anisoyl-*N'*-(5-*p*-tolyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [ATOT], *N*-*p*-methylbenzoyl-*N'*-(5-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [MBMOT] and *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-(5-*p*-methoxyphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)thiourea [BMOT].

Ligand	Ar	R
BPOT	C_6H_5	H
MBPOT	C_6H_5	CH_3
BTOT	<i>p</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	H
MBTOT	<i>p</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	CH_3
BCOT	<i>p</i> - ClC_6H_4	H
MBCOT	<i>p</i> - ClC_6H_4	CH_3
CBMOT	<i>p</i> - $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	Cl
ACOT	<i>p</i> - ClC_6H_4	OCH_3
APOT	C_6H_5	OCH_3
ATOT	<i>p</i> - $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	OCH_3
MBMOT	<i>p</i> - $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	CH_3
BMOT	<i>p</i> - $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	H

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are stable at room temperature and are non-hygroscopic. The complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but are sparingly soluble in DMF and DMSO. The low solubility of the complexes

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd	Analysis % Found/(Calcd)				Frequency (cm ⁻¹)
	Cu	C	H	N	
Cu(BPOT) (OAc) ₂	12.33	47.25	3.62	11.19	14 230, 18 290, 22 900
	(12.56)	(47.47)	(3.59)	(11.07)	
Cu(MBPOT) (OAc) ₂	11.87	48.10	3.95	10.86	14 200, 18 400, 23 010
	(12.22)	(48.50)	(3.88)	(10.78)	
Cu(BTOT) (OAc) ₂	12.03	48.15	3.76	10.54	14 480, 22 930
	(12.22)	(48.50)	(3.88)	(10.78)	
Cu(MBTOT) (OAc) ₂	11.72	49.10	3.98	10.22	14 360, 18 630, 23 020
	(11.90)	(48.48)	(4.16)	(10.49)	
Cu(BCOT) (OAc) ₂	11.59	44.82	3.04	10.54	14 040, 17 990, 23 000
	(11.76)	(44.45)	(3.17)	(10.37)	
Cu(MBCOT) (OAc) ₂	11.29	45.63	3.49	10.02	14 000, 18 450, 22 880
	(11.46)	(45.48)	(3.46)	(10.11)	
Cu(CBMOT) (OAc) ₂	10.96	43.88	3.23	9.76	14 090, 22 910
	(11.14)	(44.21)	(3.35)	(9.82)	
Cu(ACOT) (OAc) ₂	11.03	43.83	3.29	9.99	14 130, 23 040
	(11.14)	(44.21)	(3.35)	(9.82)	
Cu(APOT) (OAc) ₂	11.55	46.76	3.86	10.28	14 200, 18 200
	(11.86)	(47.05)	(3.76)	(10.45)	
Cu(ATOT) (OAc) ₂	11.68	47.81	3.92	9.99	14 150, 22 990
	(11.55)	(48.04)	(4.03)	(10.19)	
Cu(MBMOT) (OAc) ₂	11.46	47.79	3.85	10.07	14 040, 23 000
	(11.55)	(48.04)	(4.03)	(10.19)	
Cu(BMOT) (OAc) ₂	11.69	46.78	3.79	10.32	14 070, 18 360, 22 920
	(11.85)	(47.05)	(3.76)	(10.45)	

might be due to the high molecular weight associated with them. The analytical data of the complexes indicate that they have 1:1 (metal : oxidazole thiourea) stoichiometry, each of them further being associated with two acetate ions. All the complexes reveal too low molar conductivity (in DMF) (6–20 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) to be electrolytic⁴. This suggests that the two acetate ions associated with each complex are present inside the coordination sphere.

The thermograms for Cu-MBPOT, Cu-MBTOT and Cu-MBCOT complexes reveal that they have comparable thermal stability with initial decomposition temperature around 270°. The final product of decomposition above 850° corresponds, in each case, to cupric oxide.

Each ligand shows a somewhat broad, low intensity ir band around 3 100 cm^{-1} (NH). This band suffers no perceptible shift in the spectra of their Cu^{II} complexes suggesting that there is no participation of nitrogen of this group in coordination⁵. A sharp band appearing around 1 650 cm^{-1} (C=O) in the ligands undergoes, on the other hand, a lower shift by 70–90 cm^{-1} in the com-

plexes indicating coordination through oxygen of this group⁶. The low intensity ligand band around 1 590 cm^{-1} (conjugated, cyclic C=N) remains unshifted in the spectra of the complexes ruling out bonding through nitrogen of either of these groups⁷. A sharp band appearing around 1 000 cm^{-1} in the ligands has been assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ with a contribution from $\delta_{\text{C-N}}$ ⁸. This band undergoes, in the complexes, a lower shift by 60–80 cm^{-1} , indicating the involvement of thione sulphur in coordination⁹. In addition, all the complexes reveal medium or low intensity bands around 1 530 and 1 340 cm^{-1} , assigned respectively to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$ vibrations of the coordinated acetate ions. A fairly large separation of these two frequencies suggests unidentate nature of the acetate ions¹⁰. The coordination through oxygen of C=O and sulphur of C=S groups in case of all the ligands is further evidenced by the appearance, in the complexes, of medium or low intensity non-ligand bands in the far-infrared region around 500 and 350 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ vibrations respectively¹¹. Thus, it may be concluded that each of the ligands behaves towards Cu^{II}, in a neutral, bidentate man-

ner coordinating through oxygen of C=O and sulphur of C=S groups.

The μ_{eff} values of the Cu^{II} complexes are in the range 1.80–1.84 B.M. These values are within the range expected for square-planar or tetragonal Cu^{II} complexes¹².

The electronic spectral data of the complexes are incorporated in Table 1. Each of the complexes shows three or two bands that have been located around 14 000, 18 000 and/or 23 000 cm^{-1} . It is reported^{13,14} that the *d-d* bands of square-planar Cu^{II} complexes are usually observed in the frequency range 14 000–25 000 cm^{-1} . In conformity with these reports, square-planar geometry has been proposed for the present complexes, assigning, in increasing order, the frequency bands exhibited by them to the transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ of square-planar geometry. The analytical and infrared spectral data obtained in respect of the complexes render support to this proposition.

The esr spectra of each of the complexes in solid state show two peaks, one of low intensity towards left and the other of high intensity towards right. The solution spectra of the complexes in DMF are better resolved in that the low intensity peak in each of them is further split due to copper hyperfine interaction. Relevant parameters computed for all the complexes from their solution spectra are presented in Table 2. The *g* tensor values associated with the complexes are such that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ indicating that the unpaired electron lies in the metal $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital with ${}^2B_{1g}$ as the ground state. Further, the g_{\parallel} value of each of the complexes is < 2.3 suggesting covalent character of the metal-ligand bond¹⁵. The in-plane σ -bond coefficient α^2 values obtained for the complexes are in the range 0.56–0.66 and these values suggest strong covalency of the in-plane σ -bonding¹⁵⁻¹⁷. The values of in-plane π -bond coefficient β^2 , on the other hand, are in the range 0.81–0.95 indicating weak in-plane π -bonding in the complexes¹⁵.

Experimental

2-Amino-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles and their thiourea derivatives were prepared by known pro-

cedures^{18,19}. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc and m.p.

The Cu^{II} complexes with the 1,3,4-oxadiazole thiourea ligands were prepared as follows. The ligand (2 mmol) in 3 : 1 acetone-methanol mixture was added slowly with stirring to cupric acetate (1 mmol) in methanol (appropriate quantities of the solvents were used to make the ligand and the metal salt go into solution) when a pale green solid separated in each case. The contents were refluxed on a hot water-bath for about 2 h. The solid was filtered, washed with acetone-methanol mixture until the washings were free from the reactants and then dried in vacuum over fused CaCl_2 .

TABLE 2—ESR SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_0	$A_{\parallel} \times 10^{-4}$ cm^{-1}	α^2	β^2
Cu-BPOT	2.28	2.05	2.13	104.63	0.63	0.95
Cu-MBPOT	2.24	2.04	2.11	108.56	0.60	0.85
Cu-BTOT	2.28	2.06	2.13	106.25	0.64	0.95
Cu-MBTOT	2.22	2.04	2.10	103.82	0.56	0.84
Cu-BCOT	2.29	2.06	2.14	110.16	0.66	0.92
Cu-MBCOI	2.26	2.05	2.12	101.72	0.60	0.91
Cu-CBMOT	2.26	2.06	2.13	99.95	0.60	0.91
Cu-ACOT	2.22	2.05	2.11	105.60	0.57	0.81
Cu-APOT	2.23	2.05	2.11	107.33	0.59	0.83
Cu-ATOT	2.25	2.04	2.11	99.79	0.58	0.91
Cu-MBMOT	2.24	2.04	2.11	102.29	-0.58	0.87
Cu-BMOT	2.27	2.05	2.12	103.60	0.62	0.92

$g_0 = 1/3(g_{\parallel} + 2g_{\perp})$

The complexes were analysed for C, H and N at the Microanalytical Laboratory, Calcutta University, Calcutta. The copper was estimated by iodometric procedure. The molar conductance of the complexes in DMF at 10^{-3} M concentration was measured employing a Digisun DI-909 conductivity meter with Philips dip type cell. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant and corrected for diamagnetism using Pascal's constants. The thermograms of the complexes of only MBPOT, MBTOT and MBCOT could be obtained and were recorded employing a Mettler TA 3000 system. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMF) on a Shimadzu MPS 5000 spectrophotometer and esr spectra

of the complexes in polycrystalline state and in DMF at liquid nitrogen temperature on a Varian E-4 X-band instrument.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. K. Kondal Reddy and his group, Chemistry Department, Osmania University, Hyderabad, for their help in the preparation of the ligands. One of the authors (C.H.T.) is grateful to the U.G.C., New Delhi, for a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. W. AUMULLER, L. HORNER, J. KIMMIG, J. MEYER-ROHN, E. JUNGHANN and H. POHL, *Chem. Ber.*, 1952, **85**, 760; B. G. CHRISTENSEN, *Acta Pharmacol. Toxicol.*, 1945, **1**, 98; B. PÜTZER, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1937, **31**, 218; M. SHIMOTANI, *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1952, **72**, 919; K. MATSUI, *J. Soc. Org. Synth. Chem. Jpn.*, 1949, **7**, 251.
2. H. C. CALDWELL, R. J. SEIWALD and J. H. BUREKHALTER, *J. Am. Pharm. Assoc. Sci. Ed.*, 1958, **47**, 799; H. SAIKACHI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, **60**, 10692; J. METIVIER and R. BOESCH, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, **60**, 4157; J. B. O'NEAL, H. ROSEN, P. B. RUSSEL, A. C. ADMAS and A. BLUMENTHAL, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, **5**, 617.
3. H. N. PANDEY, V. J. RAM and L. MISHRA, *Indian J. Expl. Biol.*, 1979, **17**, 614.
4. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
5. S. K. SENGUPTA, S. K. SAHNI and R. N. KAPOOR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 692.
6. R. SAHAI, R. S. AGRAWAL and S. S. S. KUSHWAHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 853.
7. S. N. PODDAR and N. SAHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 57.
8. D. M. PATEL, M. M. PATEL and M. R. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 875.
9. V. B. RANA and S. K. SAHNI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 2271.
10. K. NAKAMOTO, J. FUJITA, S. TANAKA and M. KOBAYASHI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4904.
11. J. R. FERRARO, "Low-frequency Vibrations of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum, New York, 1971.
12. A. EARNSHAW, "Introduction to Magnetochemistry", Academic, New York, 1968, p. 104.
13. J. P. FACKLER, F. A. COTTON and D. W. BARHUM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 97.
14. B. C. WERDEN, E. BILLING and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 78.
15. D. KIVELSON and R. NEIMEN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1961, **35**, 149.
16. L. CASELLA, M. GULLOTTI, A. PASICINI and A. ROCKENBAUER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 2825.
17. I. S. AHUJA and S. TRIPATHI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 1060.
18. R. K. BANSAL and G. BHAGCHANDANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 277.
19. G. RAMACHANDRAI, Ph.D. Thesis, Osmania University, 1983.